

KHOJA AHRAR VALI - AS A CONTINUATOR OF NAQSHBANDI TEACHING

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Abstract: In this article, has been analyzed that every religion has made a drastic change in people's thinking in its time, and the principle of realizing the desire to live and happiness based on divine blessings has become a lifestyle. Also, in the article, the role of the Islamic factor is studied in the current situation where inter-state and inter-regional conflict of interests has intensified.

Keywords: religion, civilization, philosophical thought, doctrine, Sufism, spiritual leader

Today, the role of the Islamic factor is significant in the current situation where inter-state and inter-regional conflicts of interests have escalated. Referring to this historical process, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev stated the following at the 72nd session of the UN General Assembly: “We consider communicating the truly humanistic essence of Islam to a broad world community as the most important task.

We cherish our sacred religion as the focal point of time-honored values. We strongly condemn and we will never reconcile with those who rank our great faith together with violence and bloodshed. Islam calls us to kindness and peace, preservation of a genuine human beginning. I would like to especially note the invaluable contribution of a whole galaxy of outstanding representatives of the Central Asian Renaissance to the development of the Islamic and world civilization.

One of them - Imam Bukhari is acclaimed all over the world as the author of “Sahib Al-Bukhari”, the second most important book in Islam after the Koran. In

order to preserve and study his richest legacy, disseminate his teachings on enlightened Islam, we decided to establish the Imam Bukhari International Research Center in Samarkand”[1].

Today, we had the opportunity to study the lives, activities and works of the great saints, scientists and scholars who have flourished in our blessed land, thanks to the fact that we have achieved the happiness of self-realization. Among our great ancestors, Khoja Ahror Vali's services to humanity were also recognized. Khoja Ahror Vali lived and worked during the Timurid period. Khoja Ahror Vali was a Sufi who had his place in the development of Eastern philosophical thought of the 15th century, a major representative, reformer and follower of the Naqshbandi doctrine, who made a significant contribution to the transformation of Naqshbandi into a world doctrine.

One of the greatest service of Khoja Ahror Vali is his contribution to the transformation of Naqshbandi doctrine into a world doctrine. On the one hand, Khoja Ahror Vali was a leader of Sharia - a religious figure who fought with his whole body for the stability of the Hanafia sect, on the other hand, he was a faithful caliph of the time of the leader of the sect - Khoja Bahauddin Naqshband. In other words, in the ideological regions of the Timurid Empire, it was impossible for any idea to come into the world without his judgment and permission [2]. On the third hand, one of the great merits of Khoja Ahror Vali - those who made a worthy contribution in turning Naqshbandi doctrine into a world doctrine.

About his services, Alisher Navoi emphasized in the work “Nasoyim - ul Muhabbat”, as he is praised not only in Movarunnahr, but also in Khurasan, Iraq, Azerbaijan, even in Rome and Egypt, China and India, as a famous sheikh, scholar, teacher, teacher and a great representative of Sufism.

Every verse written by Alisher Navoi has the meaning of the universe. So, Khwaja Ahror's services in spreading the Naqshbandi order to the world is a matter worthy of study. Professor Alexander Knysh in his book “Muslim Mysticism” specifically notes the role of Khoja Ahror in the introduction of Naqshbandism in

Iran and Turkey. In northwestern Iran, the Naqshbandi sect spread slowly towards Movarounnahr and Herat. Sheikh Ali Kurdi was the disciple of Khwaja Ahrar Vali, the propagator of the Tariqat, in the city of Qazvin, which is located in the north-west of Iran [3].

Teaching of Naqshbandism began to spread among the Western Turks from the 15th century, a century after the death of the great founder of the sect, Naqshband. This was a very important step in the departure of Naqshbandism from Movarounnahr circle. In the Ottoman Empire, the Naqshbandi sect was able to attract a large number of supporters among the Turkish population in a short period of time due to its adherence to the Sunni direction of Islam and consistent adherence to Sharia rules.

The first propagator of the Naqshbandi Sufi methods in Turkey was Mulla Abdullah Ilohi Samavi (d. 1490). He studied in Samarkand under Khoja Ubaidullah Ahror. After completing his study, Mulla Abdullah Ilohi spent several years spreading the tariqat in his hometown, and later in Istanbul. He was one of the first to establish a Naqshbandiyya center in the Zeyrek mosque and attracted many supporters of the order. Despite this, Mulla Abdullah Ilohi preferred to live in divine solitude and to devote himself to religious studies. Amir Ahmad Bukhari (d. 1516) was the disciple of Ilohi. Since Ilohi's stay in Samarkand, Khoja Ahror has been following him, striving to learn from his master.

With the efforts of Amir Ahmed Bukhari, three centers of Naqshbandism were founded in Istanbul, and the members of the sect were filled with many scholars and writers.

One of them was Mahmud Lali Cholabi (died 1532) from the city of Burs. The center founded by Bukhari operated until the beginning of the 20th century. Another disciple of Khoja Ahror in Turkey was Baba Haidar Samarkandi (died 1550y). Because he had the respect of Sultan Suleiman Kanuni, the Sultan built a temple for him in the city of Ayyub. However, this center was destroyed by fire in 1912. The center was once a place of residence for Sufis from Central Asia. From

those times, the names of “Bukhara”, “Kashghar”, “Uzbeks” are still preserved. Among the Sufis who came from Central Asia was Hazini. And the Naqshbandi sect began to spread in India from the 15th century.

Khwaja Ahror achieved a certain degree of reformation and especially socialization of Naqshbandiyya teaching and he founded his branch called “Ahroriya” in its structure. The teachings of Naqshbandiyya by the Sufi and his followers spread from the Mowarounnahr region to Khorasan, Caucasus, North Caucasus, Ottoman Turks, India (including present-day Pakistan). In particular, the connection of historical figures such as Jami, Navoi and Husayn Boykara to Khoja Ahror was a great event for Naqshbandiyya doctrine. In particular, in a short period of time, the teaching of Naqshbandi gained an international character as a result of the activities of Khoja Ahror Vali and the leader of Indian Naqshbandis - Ahmad Sarhindi, known as Imam Rabbani.

And the fact that it has become a means of uniting representatives of different states and nations around a single ideology and belief has been studied separately in the researches of the Sufi scholar Ja'far Kholmo'minov. It should be noted that the spread of Naqshbandism in India is associated with the name of Muhammad Zahiruddin Babur. Mirza Babur calls him “Mulla Baba”, and this simple word hides incomparable affection. In his memoirs, Mirza Babur writes that his father, Umarshaikh Mirza, was a disciple of Khwaja Ahror, the leader of the Naqshbandi sect, and that he considered Khoja Ahror to be his spiritual leader, and that he received spiritual help from him.

Khoja Ahror's work “Anfosi Nafiya” is devoted to the explanation of the issues that are necessary for people following the path of tariqat. This treatise was also published in India along with the works of other Sufis [4]. Shafiq Yorqin, an Afghan scholar, wrote about the work “Risolai Volidiya”: “The theme of Khwaja Ahror's prose work “Risolai Volidiya” is the purification of human appearance and inner being, and Abul Fazl Allami considers it as the “jewel of the sea of enlightenment”. Mir Abdulavval, the author of the work “Masmu'ot”, came from

Nishapur and spent seven years in the service of Khoja Ahror and learned the science of tariqat from him. With the direct help of Mir Abdulavwal Khoja Ahror, he succeeded in propagating worldly teachings in Nishapur (Iran).

We mentioned above that Khwaja Ahror Vali was the successor of the teachings of Naqshbandism. In this place, it is appropriate to acknowledge the great merits of Khoja Abdulkhaliq Gijduvani, who laid the foundation stone for the teachings of the Khojagan, in the history of Sufism. Through the Khojagan sect, he aligned the sect as a whole with the Prophet Muhammad's Sunnah, purified it of various heresies and superstitions. Adherence to the Shari'a has made it a basic rule not to deviate from it. Rejecting asceticism and celibacy, he made it a condition to be with the community. He urged not to leave the world for the love of Allah. Fair bread- the need for everyone to make a living with his own work - was defined as the main requirement of the tariqa. This sect does not approve of excesses in the name of piety.

The issue of ethics was firmly established. All these things became important in the development of Sufism. Of course, it is no coincidence that the famous slogan “Dil ba yoru dast ba kor!” (“Give *your hands* to work, and *your* soul to God!”) attributed to Bahauddin Naqshband was originally proposed by Abdulkhaliq Gijduvani.

Khwaja Bahauddin Naqshband, who was educated by the spirit of Abdul Khaliq Gijduvani and founded the Naqshbandi chain, made this slogan the main rule of his sect. (Actually, Naqshbandiya itself grew out of Khojagan silsila, it is called Khojagan-Naqshbandiya, and Abdulkhaliq Ghijduvani is its leader (sarhalqai chain). The fact that Khojagan-Naqshbandiyya is based on real life conditions and the available capabilities of a person indicates that it is a solid order that meets the demands of all times and all classes.

The way of Abdulkhaliq Gijduvani, which is based on Sharia, and is free from heresy and defects, has been recognized as a document in the Tariqat for centuries and is acceptable in all groups. And that is the reason why Khojagan-

Naqshbandiya sect, widespread in Turkestan, Iran, Afghanistan, India, Turkey, Iraq, even North Africa, is still active in many countries of the world today.

So, the services of Abdukholiq Gijduvani and Khoja Ahror to the Uzbek people are extremely honorable for history, today the philosophical and social views of the Sufis, Pandu's teachings are of great importance in instilling the ideas that call for goodness and spiritual perfection in the hearts and minds of the young generation. At the present time, Naqshbandi doctrine is respected as an advanced spiritual teaching in different parts of our continent. This is a direct recognition of the services of our great ancestors and thinkers and a symbol of infinite respect for them.

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